

Special Relativity, Action-Reaction and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that E and p should be independent using two particles with different rest masses yet leading to the same p . This occurs naturally if the two particles are linked by a compressed spring in the rest frame and this spring is released. Then, in terms of independent measurements, one may measure E and p independently instead of considering $E v = p$ ($c=1$) for a particle with rest mass which makes p seem like a scaling of E . It is the physical measurement or interaction which makes E and p independent and this then leads to $-E dt + p dx$ displaying two independent terms, i.e. $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$. In other words, dt and dx in quantum mechanics seem to follow from independence of E and p which is related to the interactions/measurements. Thus, dt and dx are interaction related intervals, we argue.

In this note, we consider p_x and p_y and the notion of independence in an interaction (impulse hit) and apply it to a direction along the r vector $= x/r (e_i) + y/r (e_j)$ and a perpendicular direction $(-y/r e_i + x/r e_j)$. This leads to the notion of angular momentum. We note that if one has constrained motion in the angle ϕ (where $x=r \cos(\phi)$), then this leads to quantized angular momentum.

Independence in Measurements

It is known that p_x , p_y and p_z deliver independent impulse hits without any notion of special relativity. In special relativity, however, one has the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + p \cdot r \quad ((1))$$

If one replaces t with dt and r with $dx e_i + dy e_j + dz e_k$ (where e_i, e_j, e_k are orthogonal unit vectors in the x, y, z directions) then to demonstrate independence in an interaction, one would expect $p_x dx = p_y dy = p_z dz$. If not, then there is a relationship between them and they are not independent. Given that $E v = |p|$ for a particle with rest mass, one would at first expect that E is not independent of p , but if one thinks in terms of measurements then it is because p is linked with impulse hits, while E is linked with the distance the particle travels in a repulsive potential. Thus, we argue that one may define:

$$dt = \hbar/E \quad ((2))$$

This, in turn, ultimately leads to the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$ as discussed in Part I.

Two Dimensional Angular Co-ordinates

Given that the independence discussed above is based on interaction independence, we consider $p(r)$ and $p(\phi)$ as independent momentum components. The first acts along the vector

$r = x e_i + y e_j$, while the second acts in a perpendicular direction. In other words, one may introduce the basis:

$$e_r = x/r e_i + y/r e_j \quad ((2a)) \text{ and } e_\phi = -y/r e_i + x/r e_j \quad ((2b))$$

e_r and e_ϕ are unit vectors and are orthogonal to each other.

We then use these to find p_r and $p(\phi)$ i.e.

$$p_r = p \cdot e_r = (x (p_x)/r + y (p_y)/r) e_r \quad ((3a))$$

$$p(\phi) = p \cdot e_\phi = (x (p_y)/r - y (p_x)/r) e_\phi \quad ((3b))$$

In Cartesian co-ordinates: $p \cdot r = x (p_x) + y (p_y) \quad ((4))$

We consider $dA = dx e_i + dy e_j$ and calculate:

$$p_r e_r \cdot dA = (x (p_x)/r + y (p_y)/r) (dx + y dy) = p_r dr \quad ((5a))$$

because $dr = \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2}$

$$p(\phi) e_\phi \cdot dA = (x (p_y)/r - y (p_x)/r) (-y dx/r + x dy/r) = p(\phi) d\phi \quad ((5b))$$

Note: $-y dx/r + x dy/r = r d\phi$ if one uses $x = r \cos(\phi)$ and $y = r \sin(\phi)$

Adding ((5a)) and ((5b)) yields: $(p_x)dx + (p_y) dy \quad ((6))$

Thus, in terms of measurement independence, one should be able to consider:

$$p_r dr + p(\phi) r d\phi \quad ((7))$$

This suggests that one should have the quantum intervals:

$$\hbar/p_r \text{ and } \hbar/r p(\phi) \quad ((8)) \text{ or:}$$

$$\exp(i (p_r) r) \exp(i r p(\phi) \phi) \quad ((9))$$

Now: $r p(\phi) = x(p_y) - y (p_x) = r x p = x$ component of the usual angular momentum. ((10))

Thus, angular momentum naturally appears.

Quantum Free Particle Intervals, Constraints and Discrete Eigenvalues

It has been argued above that one has discrete spatial type intervals:

$$\hbar/\pi \text{ or } \hbar/Lz \quad ((11))$$

Given a fixed length or angular ϕ interval in a problem, \hbar/π or \hbar/Lz should fit this constraint. This suggests that only certain π or Lz values satisfy this condition and one has discreteness.

In the case of angular momentum, one has:

$$\exp(i Lz \phi) \quad ((12))$$

If a particle moves from $\phi=0$ to $\phi=2\pi$, there is no reason for the phase to differ in ((12)). Thus, one expects Lz to be an integer. This leads to quantization of Lz . The quantization of p_x appears if one has an infinite well potential which constrains $\exp(i p_x x) + \exp(-i p_x x)$ to be 0 at $x=0$ and $x=L$, the length of the box.

Conservation of Angular Momentum

The ideas of Part I which were applied to the conservation of momentum may be applied in an analogous manner to angular momentum.

Conclusion

In Part I, we considered the independence of E , p_x , p_y and p_z in terms of measurement, but used conservation of momentum to establish this measurement independence. Here, we convert from Cartesian co-ordinates in two dimensions to polar co-ordinates to see that angular momentum naturally appears. Given that \hbar/π represents ϕ intervals, one may have $d\phi = \hbar/Lz$ so that $\exp(i Lz \phi)$ should be the same at $\phi=0$ and $\phi=2\pi$. This suggests discrete integer values of Lz , e.g. $m=0,1$ etc.